

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON DELAMINATION DAMAGE BY IMPACT LOAD ON SINGLE INTERFACE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Impact damage on single interface laminate impacted by a steel projectile with hemispherical nose was studied. Mechanisms of damage were investigated by varying the depth of the interface from one ply to seven plies deep. The tensile stresses, generated by the flexural waves, caused delamination damage in an oblong shape with a high aspect ratio of 27.5 for interface only one ply deep and 2.1 for the interface 7 plies deep. The compressive stresses of flexural waves generated transverse cracks on the impact face. However, they did not exhibit delamination damage in the first three specimens with interfaces 1-3 plies deep. In other specimens, such a transverse crack on reaching the interface spread sideways to cause delamination zone of small widths giving high aspect ratio of about 18. In addition to flexural loads, shear stresses also acted on interfaces specially on specimens with interfaces close to the midplane. They tend to cause delamination damage in the shape of dumb-bells.

INTRODUCTION

Although fibre laminates are acceptable as a viable material for high technological applications in the field of aerospace, aircrafts, automobiles etc., it is still not widely accepted as materials for primary structures. In particular, delamination failure in fibre composites are caused by foreign body impacts which reduce the strength of the structures considerably.

In the last two decades, many studies¹ have been conducted on fibre composites but only a very few of them have tried to understand the mechanisms of impact damages. In 1982, Takeda et.al.² showed that transverse cracks were associated with delamination failure. In another study they showed through high speed photography that the transverse flexural waves and membrane tensile waves cause most of the delamination failure. Grady and Sun⁴ demonstrated with the help of the high speed photography that the position of an interface through the thickness significantly affects the dominant mechanism of the delamination.

In this study, one interface laminates were made from eight plies. Mechanisms of delamination were studied by varying the depth of the interface.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

1. Specimen Material

Laminates were made by the hand lay-up technique from unidirectional glass fibres/epoxy of seven different kinds, $\emptyset/9\emptyset7$, $\emptyset2/9\emptyset6$, $\emptyset3/9\emptyset5$,

Fig. 1 A two-lamina cross ply laminate.

$\emptyset_4/9\emptyset_4$, $\emptyset_5/9\emptyset_3$, $\emptyset_6/9\emptyset_2$ and $\emptyset_7/9\emptyset$. Each laminates of $18\emptyset \times 18\emptyset$ mm was impacted at the centre as shown in Fig. 1. The laminate is not symmetric about its midplane and therefore should be checked for coupling between normal stresses and shear strains which may cause warping of the plane. However, fibre configuration of this study is simple because the fibres of one lamina are normal to the fibre of other lamina. There are only two nonzero diagonal terms in coupling stiffness matrix and all the coupling terms in extensional stiffness matrix and bending stiffness matrix are zero

2. Impact Testing

A specimen panel was clamped on all its four edges before it was impacted by a 10.8 mm diameter steel projectile, 20 mm long with hemispherical nose. The projectile was accelerated in an air gun of 11 mm bore and 3.65 m length. The velocity of the projectile just prior to impact was measured through an optical technique using photo emitting diodes, receivers and a digital time counter.

The velocity of the projectile was maintained between 44 and 47 m/s (impact energies between 11.4J and 13.0J). The damage was observed by viewing the laminate against a bright light or through a reflected light.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When a projectile impacts a composite laminate it produces internal loads like bending stresses through flexural waves and shear stresses due to shear loads in the neighborhood of the impact center. They cause delamination in the damaged zone depending upon the depth d of the interface.

1. Delamination by Tensile Stresses of Flexural Waves

Although flexural waves generated by the impact of the projectile travel in all directions of the panel, the one which applies tensile stresses normal to the fibre direction in the rear panel initiates transverse cracks. In the convention of Fig. 1 the tensile stresses act in direction x_1 in the rear lamina by bending moment M_2 .

As the transverse crack propagates into the laminate and towards the impact face, it is supported by the tensile field. The effect is most prominent in the first specimen ($d=1$) with thick rear lamina. The stress distribution across the thickness is shown in Fig. 2. Thus, the

Fig. 2 Stress field of bending moment M_2 .

transverse crack in rear lamina accelerates upto the neutral plane between plies 2 and 3. The crack keeps propagating further into compressive field due to the kinetic energy it has acquired in the tensile region. On reaching the interface at $d=1$, the crack turns sideways because it cannot penetrate the fibres of the impact lamina thus causing delamination as shown in Fig. 3. The delamination zone is very long with high aspect ratio of 27.5. It is long because the transverse crack front with the aid of stiff fibres propagates faster in x_2 direction than in x_3 direction. The width of the delamination zone is small because by the time the transverse crack reaches the interface, it has already moved in compression zone beyond the neutral plane for a large distance of more than 1.5 plies. Thus, the crack with low energy does not cause large delamination damage.

The case of second specimen ($d=2$) is similar except with a slight difference that the interface is very close to the neutral plane (Fig. 2). Not much of the energy of the transverse crack is dissipated by the compression zone and, therefore, the resulting delamination cracks penetrate farther. This also explains the decrease in aspect ratio when the interface depth is increased from one ply to two as shown in Fig. 4. The vertical bars show the extent of scatter for the two sets of tests conducted.

In case of third specimen the transverse crack front does not enter the compressive region at all and, therefore, when it turns into the delamination crack, it goes farther in comparison to the case of second specimen. For the case of interface at midplane ($d=4$), the damage zone in Fig. 3 shows that its length is about 20% smaller in comparison to other cases discussed so far. This can be explained by noting that the transverse crack fronts are not able to propagate far enough in x_2 direction due to less time available for crack propagation through the thickness in the rear lamina. Further, delaminated area in Fig. 3 is observed to be like a dumb-bell. This is caused by the combination of damages from (i) shear stresses and the (ii) tensile stresses of flexural waves. The effect of shear stress is discussed subsequently.

Fig. 3 Delamination areas with varying interface depth from 1 to 7 plies.

In specimen of interfaces at greater depths ($d=5,6,7$) the length of delamination area decreases with depth d (Fig. 3). This occurs due to two reasons. First, as explained for the fourth specimen, the crack in depth directions moves by smaller distances which, in turn, does not provide enough time for crack front to propagate length wise. Second, the tensile stresses are much lower in comparison to those of thick rear lamina (Fig. 2). Further, the damage zone of seventh specimen is close to an ellipse with low aspect ratio of 2.1. The dumb-bell shape was no longer observed because the interface was very close the rear face and the shear stresses were not high. In contrast to only one or two cracks in $d=1, 2, 3$ specimens more number of transverse crack along the fibre direction of rear lamina were observed.

The shape of the damage area is governed mainly by the failure through the tensile stresses. Thus, Fig. 4 shows monotonic decrease in the aspect ratio as the interface depth is increased.

Fig. 4 Aspect ratio of delamination areas.

2. Delamination by Compressive Stresses of Flexural Waves

Transverse cracks were also generated at the impact face in x_1 direction by the compressive stress fields probably through the mechanism of buckling. These cracks propagated into the laminate thickness. The growth of such cracks is not well understood but they are not expected to be fast moving and possess large energies. The first three specimens are not observed to have delamination growth out of the front surface cracks because compressive stresses due to bending moment M_1 are low as shown in Fig. 5. On reaching interfaces the compressive transverse cracks of specimens 4, 5 and 6 spread sideways on the interfaces to cause delamination damage as shown in Fig. 6 for specimen no. 6. As expected, the spread was very narrow giving a very high aspect ratio of about 18. Such delaminations were not observed in specimen 7 because the tensile field around the cracks transverse nullifies the compressive stresses.

Fig. 5 Stress field of bending moments M_1 .

3. Delamination by Shear Stresses

Shear forces generated by the impacting projectile develop high shear stress τ_{31} and τ_{32} (Fig. 7) on interfaces. Delamination may also be studied through texture of parallel lines created due to failure of the interfaces.

Interplay between mode I cracks generating through bending stresses and mode II cracks through direct shear loads, has been studied through the texture of fracture surfaces. However, some more work is required to conclude with certainty. In the first specimen, the textured lines are parallel to the direction x_1 generated by mode I transverse cracks of rear lamina spreading on the interface. Texture of damaged area in specimen 2 is similar except around the centre of impact; the textured lines are parallel to x_2 and they are caused by high shear stress τ_{31} . In specimens 4-7 lines corresponding to τ_{32} are also observed parallel to x_1 . One such set of lines are seen in specimen 6 (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Delamination area developed by compressive transverse cracks along x_1 direction.

Further, it was observed that fibres right under the nose of projectile sag considerably to relieve shear load on a narrow corridor in x_1 direction. Consequently, the delaminated area takes the shape of a dumb-bell.

Fig. 7 Shear stresses at the interfaces.

Fig. 8 Variation of delamination damage area with interface depth.

4. Overall Delamination Area

Overall delamination caused by tensile and compressive stresses and shear stresses are shown in Fig. 8 in which the vertical bars give the scatter for the two sets of experiments conducted. As described earlier, the delamination in the first specimen ($d=1$) caused by the transverse crack originated at the rear surface is small because the crack travels in a compressive stress field through a considerable distance prior to its turning into delamination crack. In specimens 2 and 3, the transverse cracks do not lose their energy against the compressive stress and therefore the delaminated areas are larger. In specimens 4, 5 and 6, delamination due to shear stresses were considerable and its combined effect with delamination generated by the tensile transverse cracks show large area damages in Fig. 8. In the

specimen(d=7) delamination area is smaller because the shear stress is no longer prominent; the transverse tensile cracks are not able to become long as they travel only a short distance to the interface. Thus it was observed that an interface slightly off from the midplane and towards the rear face shows the maximum delamination.

5. Dent Formation at the Point of Impact

A dent was observed to be formed under the hemispherical nose of the projectile but not much of fibre breakage was noticed within or around the dent. The size of the dent was observed to be small when interface was very close to the impact face. In such cases, the fibres of the thin impact lamina were supported underneath on the thick rear lamina with its fibres placed normal. On the other hand, the dent was observed to be considerably bigger for laminates with interface far away from the impact face. The fibres near the impact face were no longer well supported by the cross fibres. In Fig. 3, the dent as well as associated debonding increases as d is increased from 1 to 7. The white zones around the dent were produced due to sagging of fibres and resulting debonding between the fibres and the epoxy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research work has been funded by the Structural Panel of Aeronautics Research and Development Board, Government of India. The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Dr. K. Rajaiah of ARDB, Bangalore, Dr. N. S. Venkataraman of MIT, Madras and Dr. K. Rama Rao of DRDL, Hyderabad for their help and encouragement in carrying out this work.

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